

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

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MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI TIZIMLASHTIRILGAN TAHDIDLAR.....	40
Qodirov Tuyg'un Uzoqovich, Nabiyev Bexzod Shavkatovich	
SANOAT TARMOQLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INNOVATSIYA VA TEXNOLOGIK MODERNIZATSIYANING O'RNI	44
Boboqulov Sanjar Bahromqulovich	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI BAHOLASHNING USLUBIYOTI VA UNING SOLIQ TIZIMIDA QO'LLANILISHI	49
To'xtabayev Oybek Odilovich	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH BO'YICHA ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR.....	56
Ismailov Bobir Salomovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY JIHATLARI	62
Yangiboyev F.B.	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY SALOHİYATDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	68
Turayev Og'abek Kaxramonovich	
XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAJRIBASI.....	75
Yusupova Feruza Yo'ldoshevna	
BANK XIZMATLARI SIFATINI BOSHQARISHNING INTEGRATSION VA ADAPTIV MODEL.....	83
Ibroximov Ilxomjon Shavkatjon o'g'li	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLAR ASOSIDA BAHOLASH	89
Qidirniyazov Ajiniyaz Sherniyazovich	
ICHKI NAZORAT VA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDAGI XAVFLARNI BOSHQARISH	94
Islamova Nargiza Mirzaxidovna	
TURIZMNING MINTAQADA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI	104
Rasulova Muxabbat Teshabayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISH ORQALI INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING HOZIRGI KUNDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	111
Begamov S.X.	
RETHINKING JOB CREATION: ONTOLOGICAL AND EPISTEMOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF MACROECONOMIC EMPLOYMENT ANALYSIS.....	116
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
HUDUDIY TURIZM KLASTERLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA ULARNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	125
Ro'zimova Xusnora Mirzobek qizi	
SUG'URTACHILIK VA O'ZBEKISTONDA SUG'URTA SEKTORINING HOLATI.....	129
O'runboyeva Sotima Alisher qizi	
GO'SHT VA GO'SHT MAHSULOTLARINI SANOAT USULIDA QAYTA ISHLASHDA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBALARI.....	134
Xaydarova Sitora Suranbay qizi	
KORXONALAR QIYMATINI BAHOLASH VA BOZOR BAHOSINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	139
Abduraxmanov Sherzodbek Ravshanovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIK VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK UYG'UNLIGI.....	145
Jamaldinova Asalxon Saliyevna	
2025-YILDA O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN ENG YAXSHI 10 TA TRANSPORT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA INNOVATSIYALARI	151
Mamasaliyeva Mukaddas Ibadullayevna, Beketov Timur Kazakbayevich	

MAHSULOT TANNARXINI ANIQLASHNING INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN YONDASHUVLARI: AN'ANAVIY VA ZAMONAVIY TIZIMLAR QIYOSIY TAHLILI	155
Tulyaganov Abdumalik Abdiraximovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННО-ИНВЕСТИЦИОННАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ В НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИХ ПОДХОДОВ	163
Хайдарова Ёркиной Аскар кизи	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INNOVATSION TADBIRKORLIKNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING FISKAL VA INSTITUTSIONAL MEKANIZMLARI	170
Mamatova Nodira Mirzavaliyevna	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА И УСТОЙЧИВЫЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИИ: ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ МОДЕЛИ ПЕРЕХОДА ТЕПЛИЧНЫХ ХОЗЯЙСТВ ТАШКЕНТСКОЙ АГЛОМЕРАЦИИ НА СОЛНЕЧНЫЕ СИСТЕМЫ ЭНЕРГОСНАБЖЕНИЯ	178
Срджиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна, Абдувалиева Зилола Абдуллаевна	
МАМЛАКАТИМИЗДА QISHLOQ HUDUDLARIDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	186
Yuldashova Nilufar Ziyabayevna	
RIVOJLANISHDA RAQOBAT EMAS, BALKI HAMKORLIKNING USTUVORLIGI: NAZARIY VA AMALIY TAHLIL	190
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich	
IJTIMOY HIMOYA QAMROVINI KENGAYTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI VA "QAMRAB OLINMAGAN O'RTA QATLAM" MUAMMOSI	196
Bafoev Farrux Jo'raqulovich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA EKOLOGIK BOSHQARUVNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	202
Shanazarova Gulyoraxon Baxtiyarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON STARTAP EKOTIZIMIDA INVESTITSIYA JALB QILISH JARAYONINING INSTITUTSIONAL MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH MEKANIZMLARI	208
Xoliqova Xurshidaxon Xayotjon qizi	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA STARTAP EKOTIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHLTLARI	214
Usmanov Gafurjon Shavkatovich	
QURILISHDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH VA SIFATNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHI	220
Buriyev Xakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ilxom Achilovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSION MUHITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING STRATEGIYALARI	225
Xolov Sherali Axrorboyevich	
2010-2024-YILLARDA O'ZBEKISTONDA TO'QIMACHILIKNI INVESTITSIYALASHNING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI	229
Ashurov Shuhratbek Qudrat o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI	233
Sherbekova Kamola Norbekovna	
AHOLI MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGI DARAJASI VA UNI BAHOLASHNING ILMIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	243
Abduvoxidov Akmal Abdulazizovich	
MARKAZIY BANK KURS SIYOSATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI	249
Saydullayev Nodirbek Narzullaevich	
O'ZBEKISTON MINTAQALARIDA BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SALOHİYATI VA MUAMMOLARI	258
Raupov Shuxrat Soyibovich	
ЭКОТУРИЗМ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ	264
Абидова Дилфуза Игамбердиевна, Рахматуллаева Зулайхо Хасан кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: BUSINESS CHANGE IN THE REGIONS	270
Abdullayev Muzaffar Abdujabbarovich	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIK MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLASHDA IOT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	273
Mirzaev Dilshod Artikovich	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ СТАРТАП-ПРОЕКТОВ В ВУЗАХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	279
Касимова Наргиза Сабитджановна	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	284
Ismoyilova Mahliyo Oybek qizi	
BOSHQARUVDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR (OLIV TA'LIM MISOLIDA).....	289
Kariyeva Gulnora Abdullayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORPORATIV MIJOZLARGA XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI VA ASOSIY TENDENSIYALARI.....	295
Qurbonov Odilbek Ro'zmatovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SPORT FEDERATSIYALARI VA ASSOTSIATSIYALARINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH YO'LLARI.....	302
Umed Farmonkulovich Radjabov	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA QARATILGAN IQTISODIY MEKANIZMNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ULARNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI.....	307
Mullayeva Mexrangiz Axtam qizi	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH YO'LLARI (NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	313
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Muradova Nazira Raximjanovna	
RAQAMLI MARKETING VA ONLAYN PLATFORMALAR ORQALI EKOTURISTIK MAJMUALARNI OMMALASHTIRISH TRENDI.....	318
Xolmatova Parvina Asliddin qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGI STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI VA ULARNI YECHIMLAR.....	323
Normurzayev Umid Xolmurzayevich	
РАЗВИТИЕ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО БАНКОВСКОГО ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ В ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ НА ОСНОВЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА КАК ФАКТОР РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	327
Бахтиёров Худайберган Хамдам угли	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLARDA TRANSFERTLARGA QARAMLIK DARAJASINI VAHOLASH (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	335
Xudoyqulov Hamidjon Abdullayevich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNI BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI.....	342
Tajibaev Berdax Asqarbay uli	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA INNOVATSION JARAYONLARNI JADALLASHTIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	347
Ashurova Maftuna Ortiq qizi	
STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING CAPITAL EFFICIENCY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS: DIGITALIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT INTEGRATION.....	352
Sadullaeva Mokhinur Aziz kizi	
TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT AND SME INTERNATIONALIZATION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW.....	358
Abduxafizova Madinabonu Mirabbos qizi	

TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT AND SME INTERNATIONALIZATION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract. Through a thorough analysis of the literature, this study investigates the connection between technology-related competences and the internationalization of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Existing research is still geographically focused in developed nations and conceptually divided, despite the growing recognition of innovation and digital transformation as drivers of export performance. In order to close this gap, the study uses a structured PRISMA-based selection procedure and quality filtering criteria (Q1–Q3, ABDC, ABS, SSCI-indexed journals) to examine 40 peer-reviewed journal papers published between 2005 and 2025. The results show that innovation capacity, digital transformation, and strategic technology management are important factors that influence the global expansion of SMEs. However, transition economies like Uzbekistan, where institutional circumstances and degrees of digital maturity may have a major impact on these relations, have received little empirical attention. Major theoretical stances, prevailing methodological patterns, and new research needs in the subject are all identified in the review.

Key words: SMEs, Technology management, Digital transformation, Internationalisation, Export performance, Systematic literature review.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot kichik va o'rta korxonalar (KO'K)ning xalqaro faoliyati bilan texnologiyaga oid kompetensiyalar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni adabiyotlarni chuqur tahlil qilish orqali o'rganadi. Innovatsiya va raqamli transformatsiya eksport samaradorligining muhim omillari sifatida tobora ko'proq e'tirof etilayotganiga qaramay, mavjud tadqiqotlar asosan rivojlangan davlatlarga qaratilgan hamda konseptual jihatdan tarqoq holatda qolmoqda. Ushbu bo'shliqni to'ldirish maqsadida tadqiqot PRISMA asosidagi tanlash jarayoni va sifat mezonlari (Q1–Q3, ABDC, ABS, SSCI indekslangan jurnallar) orqali 2005–2025 yillar oralig'ida chop etilgan 40 ta ilmiy maqolani tahlil qiladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, innovatsion salohiyat, raqamli transformatsiya va strategik texnologiya menejmenti KO'Klarning xalqaro kengayishiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Biroq O'zbekiston kabi o'tish iqtisodiyotiga ega mamlakatlarda, institutsional sharoitlar va raqamli yetuklik darajasi ushbu munosabatlarga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin bo'lsa-da, empirik tadqiqotlar yetarli emas. Sharhda asosiy nazariy yondashuvlar, ustuvor metodologik tendensiyalar va kelgusidagi tadqiqot yo'nalishlari aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: KO'K, texnologiya menejmenti, raqamli transformatsiya, xalqaro faoliyat, eksport samaradorligi, tizimli adabiyotlar sharhi.

Аннотация. Данное исследование изучает взаимосвязь между технологическими компетенциями и интернационализацией малых и средних предприятий (МСП) на основе комплексного анализа научной литературы. Несмотря на растущее признание инноваций и цифровой трансформации как факторов, способствующих экспортной эффективности, существующие исследования в основном сосредоточены на развитых странах и остаются концептуально фрагментированными. Для устранения данного пробела в работе применяется структурированная процедура отбора на основе PRISMA и критерии качества (журналы Q1–Q3, ABDC, ABS, индексируемые в SSCI), что позволило проанализировать 40 рецензируемых статей, опубликованных в период с 2005 по 2025 год. Результаты показывают, что инновационный потенциал, цифровая трансформация и стратегическое управление технологиями являются важными факторами, влияющими на международную экспансию МСП. Однако в странах с переходной экономикой, таких как Узбекистан, где институциональные условия и уровень цифровой зрелости могут существенно влиять на данные взаимосвязи, эмпирических исследований пока недостаточно. В обзоре также определены ключевые теоретические подходы, преобладающие методологические тенденции и перспективные направления дальнейших исследований.

Ключевые слова: МСП, управление технологиями, цифровая трансформация, интернационализация, экспортная эффективность, систематический обзор литературы.

INTRODUCTION

The competitive environment among small and medium-sized enterprises, or SMEs, has changed dramatically because of the quick development of digital technology. Technological prowess is becoming a key factor in determining global competitiveness rather than a peripheral resource in more globalized marketplaces. SMEs can lower conventional barriers to entering overseas markets, increase coordination effectiveness, and improve responsiveness to global demand with the help of online resources, platforms, and based on data systems. Technology-related skills are therefore becoming more widely acknowledged as important facilitators of SME internationalization.

According to current research, digitalization has a direct and indirect impact on international trade through increases in organizational effectiveness and productivity. However, evidence suggests that some forms of innovation, especially product innovation, may have greater effects on export propensity. Innovation is also crucial in determining export performance. Additionally, involvement in global digital platforms has given SMEs new avenues for internationalization, however the results seem to be mostly dependent on the internal capabilities and adaptable tactics of the firms [1]. The literature is still conceptually and methodologically discontinuous despite increased scholarly attention. While some studies focus on institutional and contextual factors that influence the development of SMEs, especially in transition economies, others use resource-based approaches to explain how technology assets create competitive advantages. The necessity for organizational adaption during international expansion is further highlighted by research on business model transition. Nevertheless, these research areas frequently develop simultaneously, with no integrated synthesis of the ways in which organizational, technological, and environmental factors work together to influence SME internationalization. A comprehensive examination is required in light of this fragmentation in order to map systematic patterns in the discipline, identify prevailing theoretical frameworks, and consolidate current knowledge. An updated synthesis that incorporates technology management, innovation capabilities, digital platforms, and export performance views is still necessary, even if previous evaluations have looked at digitalization and SME internationalization [2]. In developing and transition economy environments, such a review is especially essential for directing future empirical studies and for influencing policy actions. To investigate how technology-related capabilities impact the results of SME internationalization, this study performs a systematic literature assessment of 40 peer-reviewed journal publications published between 2005 and 2025. In addition to identifying future study paths in this developing topic, the review aims to present a descriptive as well as thematic review of current research.

RQ1: How has existing literature examined the relationship between technology-related capabilities and SME internationalization?

RQ2: What theoretical perspectives and research gaps characterize this field?

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is becoming more widely acknowledged that technological capabilities are key factors in the internationalization of SMEs. Research shows that strategic integration of electronic resources into organizational processes is a factor of export performance that goes beyond basic technology adoption. Research indicates that companies that use data-driven systems and digital infrastructures are better able to recognize overseas market prospects and manage global operations. Empirical research, however, shows that the impact of digitalization is contingent upon the firm's internal capabilities structure and strategy alignment [3].

Additionally, recent studies indicate that technology promotes internationalization by increasing operational efficiency and productivity. Specifically, companies that successfully integrate digital systems into their value chains outperform those who adopt technology superficially in terms of export performance. This contrast emphasizes how crucial it is to view technology not as a stand-alone instrument but as a managed organizational resource [4].

One of the main ways that technological capabilities are converted into global competitiveness is through innovation. There is evidence that the effects of various types of innovation on export propensity varies. In contrast to process or innovation in services, product innovation seems to have a greater impact on global expansion [5]. This implies that outward-focused innovation methods may be more important for differentiation in international markets. Furthermore, a company's capacity to mobilize technological resources and transform knowledge into commercial outputs frequently shapes its innovation capabilities. Although the mediation function of innovation among technology and export success is implicitly acknowledged in a number of empirical studies, there is still a lack of integrative synthesis among investigations. This demonstrates the necessity of methodically integrating the ways in which innovation operates within the larger technology internationalization relationship.

The literature is based on a variety of theoretical stances. Arguments based on resources highlight a company's unique technological resources and competencies as points of advantages in global marketplaces [6]. Other studies take institutional viewpoints into account, especially in transition economies where SME development pathways are shaped by contextual restrictions [7]. The area lacks a coherent integration of diverse perspectives despite theoretical diversity, which leads to fragmented empirical findings.

Strategic change and global expansion have been used to analyze management of technology and digital change in SMEs. According to Matarazzo, Penco, and Profumo, digital transformation is not just operational but also closely linked to strategic orientation and internationalization logic in SMEs. Digital tools facilitate international market sensing, engagement with clients, and organizational reconfiguration, but the results rely on how SMEs match digital initiatives with strategic objectives and priorities for international expansion [8].

An alternative viewpoint is provided by studies on technologies from Industry 4.0 (IoT and AI) in SMEs, which indicate that sophisticated technologies are frequently underutilized because of resource and capability limitations. Because full-scale electronic integration necessitates stronger data infrastructure, expertise, and managerial preparedness, survey-based synthesis shows that SMEs usually approach staggered implementation, beginning with restricted, machine-level deployment and progressively growing. The concept that maturity and implementation strategy, rather than just technology presence, determine worldwide competitiveness from modern technologies is supported by this line of inquiry [9].

Technology-enabled worldwide competitiveness increasingly overlaps with financial, environmental, and social goals, according to recent systematic review data that links SMEs, digital change, and sustainability (typically defined via triple bottom line reasoning). According to this stream, digital technologies can help with stakeholder responsiveness, resource efficiency, and accountability. However, when SMEs attempt to pursue sustainability and internationalization at the same time, they encounter trade-offs and capability gaps, indicating the need for more fully integrated strategic frameworks [10].

Methodologically, some studies analyze SME digital transformation readiness and impediments using structured decision techniques. Fuzzy logic-based work on SME digitalization, for instance, shows how uncertainty and subjective managerial assessments (such as "high readiness" and "moderate barriers") can be methodically converted into formal rules for making decisions. This method is useful because judgments about SME transformation sometimes depend on insufficient information and subjective evaluations; modeling these factors explains why comparable SMEs could choose various digital paths with disparate global results [11].

Lastly, qualitative cross-case studies employing network-based frameworks (such as the A-R-A models) demonstrate that relationship-level transformation, rather than firm-level acceptance alone, is often the catalyst for internationalization and digitalization. This evidence indicates that technology-related international expansion may depend not just on internal digital investments but also on how SMEs reconfigure operations, resources, and actor connections across borders by categorizing changes into different magnitude levels (e.g., incremental versus more profound transformations) [12].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study synthesizes previous research on technology-related competences and SME internationalization using a systematic review of the literature (SLR) methodology. A systematic and open review process was used to guarantee methodological consistency, rigor, and reproducibility. The review adheres to accepted systematic review concepts, such as multi-stage screening, a clear search method, and predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Google Scholar served as the main database for the literature search. Because of its extensive coverage of peer-reviewed scholarly articles in the fields of business, management, and economics, Google Scholar was chosen.

The following keyword combinations were used in the search:

- ✓ "technology management"
- ✓ "digital transformation"
- ✓ "digital capability"
- ✓ "innovation"
- ✓ "SME" or "small and medium enterprises"
- ✓ "internationalization"
- ✓ "export performance"

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The ones that follow inclusion criteria were used to guarantee quality and relevance:

- 1) The study specifically targets SMEs.
- 2) Technology, digitalization, innovation, or capabilities relating to technology are examined in this article.

- 3) These elements are directly related to export performance or internationalization, according to the study.
- 4) A peer-reviewed journal published the work.

The following research was not included:

- 1) Studies that only look at big businesses.
- 2) Studies of trade that are solely macroeconomic and lack a firm-level viewpoint.
- 3) Book chapters, conference papers, other sources without peer assessment.
- 4) Studies with no obvious link between technology and internationalization.

To guarantee openness, reproducibility, and scientific rigor in the article selection process, this study adheres to the preferred reporting items for Systematical Reviews and Meta-Analyses, or PRISMA, criteria. A comprehensive multi-stage screening process comprising phases for identification, assessment of eligibility, and inclusion was used to carry out the evaluation. Only peer-reviewed journal papers that were indexed in reputable academic rankings were incorporated to improve academic quality and dependability. In particular, the review included research from: Journals in Scopus in Q1, Q2, and Q3, journals ranked by ABDC (A*, A, B), journals with an ABS ranking (1–4), Web of Sciences journals that are indexed by SSCI.

Stage	Description	Number of Articles
Identification	Records identified through Google Scholar search	214
Identification	Additional records identified through reference screening	18
Screening	Records after duplicates removed	192
Screening	Records excluded after title and abstract screening	103
Eligibility	Full-text articles assessed for eligibility	89
Eligibility	Full-text articles excluded (not meeting SME–technology–internationalisation criteria or journal quality filters)	49
Included	Final studies included in systematic review	40

There were several phases to the screening procedure. At first, many possibly pertinent studies were produced via keyword searches. Articles that were blatantly irrelevant were eliminated by screening abstracts and titles. A full-text examination was then conducted to determine eligibility based on the predetermined standards. Studies that didn't meet the inclusion criteria were eliminated, and duplicates were eliminated. A final collection of forty peer-reviewed publications was kept for analysis following the application of all screening phases. Descriptive and theme synthesis methods were used to analyze the chosen articles. Descriptive study looked at regional distribution, methodological techniques, prevailing theoretical frameworks, and publishing trends. To find conceptual patterns, recurrent ideas, and new research needs in the literature, a thematic analysis was performed. A systematic grasp of how technology-related capacities are conceptualized and empirically investigated in connection to SME internationalization is made possible by this integrated analytical approach.

Forty peer-reviewed papers published between 2005 through 2025 made up the final sample. After 2018, publication activity dramatically increased, indicating a rise in scholarly interest in SME internationalization and digital transformation. While more current study emphasizes digital platforms, Industry 4.0 technologies, and capability development, earlier studies mostly concentrated on innovation and export performance. Geographically, transitional especially Central Asian economies were underrepresented in empirical research, which was mostly carried out in European environments. This disparity indicates possible geographic study gaps and emphasizes the contextual focus of current studies. Most studies used quantitative research designs, often utilizing SEM (structural equation modeling) and survey data. A lesser percentage depended on systematic literature reviews or qualitative case studies.

According to the analysis, the most often used theoretical framework in the area is the Resource-Based View (RBV). Research utilizing RBV conceptualizes digital resources and technology skills as company-specific assets that produce competitive advantage in global markets. Additionally, innovation theory is crucial, especially when it comes to elucidating how technical advancement affects export performance. Studies on economies in transition, where institutional quality and regulatory contexts affect the development paths of SMEs, are where institutional perspectives are most prevalent. Furthermore, capability-based approaches and platform theory have been more popular in recent years, especially in studies looking at involvement in digital platforms and the development of adaptive strategies.

The empirical landscape is dominated by quantitative survey-based research. Mediation and moderation effects are commonly tested using structural equation modeling (SEM), which includes either covariance-based or partial least-squares techniques. The most prevalent dependent variables are international performance,

export intensity, and exporting propensity. The three separate constructions that are most studied are technology adoption, digital transformation, and innovation capability. Nonetheless, there are significant differences in operationalization between research, which suggests measurement irregularities in the field. Although less common, qualitative research offers deeper insight into the processes of capability building and strategic adaptation. Recent systematic reviews indicate that the field is becoming more mature.

Technology-related competences are crucial in determining the results of SME internationalization, according to the systematic review. Digital transformation, innovation capacity, and engagement in digital platforms stand out as key factors impacting export performance across the evaluated research. However, the majority of current research focuses on industrialized economies, with transition environments like Uzbekistan receiving little empirical attention. This geographic disparity raises the possibility that the institutional and physical realities encountered by SMEs in developing nations are not well captured by the theoretical models currently in use. The results show that adopting new technologies does not ensure global competitiveness. Instead, developing organizational capabilities, managing digital resources strategically, and coordinating innovation efforts with market expansion plans are all essential for global success.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

To investigate how technology-related competencies impact SME internationalization, this study conducted a systematic review of 40 peer-reviewed journal articles. The results show that the key factors influencing export performance are innovation capacity, digital transformation, and strategic use of technology. Nonetheless, literature is still geographically concentrated in affluent nations and theoretically dispersed. According to the review, there is a substantial research gap concerning transition situations, especially Uzbekistan, where institutional circumstances and degrees of digital maturity are different from those in developed economies. Therefore, to better understand SME internationalization in emerging nations, future research should create context-sensitive frameworks that incorporate technological competence, innovation channels, and institutional dynamics. This study offers a methodical framework for next empirical investigations and the formulation of policies targeted at enhancing Uzbekistan's SME international competitiveness.

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